

Pitfalls of adopting Temperature Neutrality as a climate target

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Summary

Based on evidence gathered over seven years exploring pathways to climate neutrality in Ireland's land sector, including modelling of agriculture and land use scenarios for Ireland's Climate Change Advisory Council (CCAC), we are highly concerned that Ireland's climate policy is drifting away from established international frameworks into risky territory - without proper scrutiny. Specifically, we strongly oppose the adoption of a Temperature Neutrality (TN) approach to define Ireland's long-term climate neutrality target, as proposed by the CCAC. In this briefing note, and drawing from a recent peer-reviewed paper led by our group in University of Galway¹, we outline why adoption of a TN approach would:

undermine global food security, by appropriating methane "emission rights" from food insecure countries who desperately need to grow their own agriculture sectors to meet basic needs

misdirect national policy away from action to offset Ireland's agri-food sector emissions indigenously, exposing the sector to huge reputational risks, and exposing Irish tax-payers to high compliance costs under EU emissions regulations

misdirect policy away from substantial opportunities to build CO₂ negative bio-based industries that could create new revenue for farmers and rural Ireland, whilst offsetting agri-food emissions

Introduction

Ireland's Climate Change Advisory Council (CCAC) has proposed using a national "Temperature Neutrality" (TN) approach as a Paris Agreement aligned target to meet the legally binding national climate neutrality goal. A national TN approach aims to stabilise Ireland's contribution to global temperature increase (at a high per capita level), rather than decrease it. As such, TN is known as "no additional warming".

This approach has gained traction among wealthy, animal sourced food product export-oriented countries, such as Ireland and New Zealand, due to substantial methane emissions arising from these activities. Methane is a short-lived greenhouse gas (GHG), remaining in the atmosphere for approximately 10 years, relative to CO₂ which persists for many hundreds of years. As such, it is argued, that methane needs to be accounted differently to long-lived gases such as CO₂.

However, there are more transparent and internationally-defendable approaches to account for methane separately, such as a split-gas target^{2,3}, and **TN deviates radically from net-zero emission trajectories for Ireland**. Adopting TN therefore risks costly policy misdirection that will be difficult to reverse. Our recent peer-reviewed study¹ challenges the assumption that a national TN approach is Paris Agreement aligned. We also outline why TN introduces high uncertainty into agriculture and land use policy, and could result in a lost decade of climate action to mitigate foreseeable economic and reputational damage (for the country, and the agri-food sector in particular).

International equity & global food security

The Paris Agreement requires peaking and then declining global temperatures, not stabilising them at today's levels. A national TN approach is therefore **not aligned with the Paris Agreement**. Additionally, under Article 4

¹ Duffy et al. (2025). [10.1088/1748-9326/adf12d](https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/adf12d)

² Prudhomme et al. (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.113058>

³ Bishop et al. (2024). <https://www.nature.com/articles/s43247-024-01275-0>

of the Paris Agreement, Ireland has agreed to maximise ambition around climate mitigation, as a high capacity (wealthy) country. TN effectively passes the buck on mitigation to other countries, and is likely to be perceived as shirking international responsibility on climate action.

The EU and Ireland share the goal of climate neutrality integral to the Paris Agreement. However, the EU definition of “climate neutrality” is unambiguously net-zero GHG emissions by 2050. Attempting to redefine Ireland's climate target could be viewed as “game playing”. This will not only damage credibility and trust with our European partners, but sets Ireland up for high future compliance costs as the TN pathway increasingly deviates from net-zero GHG pathways.

A national TN target implicitly “**grandfathers**” Ireland’s already **high methane emissions**. It allows Ireland to claim a disproportionately high per-capita share of tomorrow’s methane budget based on the share that we already have. Ireland’s agri-food sector is an important source of animal sourced food products internationally, and revenue to the country. However, our study shows that Ireland exports 90% of those products, with less than 1% of exports reaching low-income, food-insecure regions. The vast majority serve high-income consumers overseas. Thus, by effectively appropriating methane “emissions rights” from food insecure countries that need to grow their agricultural sectors to feed their own populations, **TN actually undermines global food security**.

Misdirection of national agriculture and land use policy

TN is a moving target because the point at which Ireland causes “no further warming” strongly depends on actions taken in other countries to control methane emissions. Our results show that national emissions trajectories that achieve a TN target are highly sensitive to assumptions about future emissions trajectories from other countries. The implicit requirement to remodel and update Ireland’s TN target based on updates in global emissions trajectories introduces **unnecessary uncertainty, and undermines stable target setting**. Land use change takes time, so effective agriculture and land use policy should be informed by stable, long-term targets.

Recent modelling at the University of Galway^{4,5} has clearly shown that achieving robust climate targets will require a large and sustained land use transition, and the **development of CO₂ removal mechanisms**. In many cases, such as forestry, momentum on removals takes decades to establish. TN implies much less need for CO₂ removal over the next three decades, **risking a lost generation of critical action** to turn Ireland’s land sector into part of the climate solution. In fact, we have shown that **ambitious pathways do exist to maintain Ireland’s agri-food exports** whilst going considerably beyond a TN target, achieving a split-gas net-zero target by 2050, and a full net-zero GHG emissions by 2070 if ongoing investment in CO₂ removal is made^{6,7}. Such pathways have been outlined in the Carbon Budget working group report submitted to the CCAC⁸, and in the Land Use Review Phase 2 (report under Ministerial review). In policy discussions we have been privy to, TN has already been invoked to undermine the discussion of such pathways, and in turn the implied need for a national land use strategy. In this regard, we see a huge risk that TN is used to delay critical action in the land sector, kicking a growing problem on to the next generation of farmers (and society more widely).

Ireland does face a particular challenge in the scale of agriculture and land use emissions relative to many other countries, but is not completely alone in this. Denmark for example faces a similar challenge. Rather than attempting to water down their national climate neutrality target, Denmark is investing in CO₂ removal – via afforestation and technical pathways such as bioenergy with carbon capture and storage and biochar – and ambitious agricultural reform through a methane tax (reinvested into climate friendly farming). Ireland risks

⁴ Duffy et al. (2022). <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41893-022-00946-0>

⁵ Styles et al. (2024). <https://www.epa.ie/publications/research/climate-change/research-457-towards-a-climate-neutral-land-sector-by-2050scenarios-quantifying-land-use--emissions-transitions-towards-equilibrium-with-removals-sequester.php>

⁶ Henn et al. (2025). <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0048969725007508>

⁷ Styles et al. (2025). https://task40.ieabioenergy.com/wp-content/uploads/sites/29/2025/05/IEA-Bioenergy_Intertask_BECCUS_Phase2_Science-and-Policy-Report_final.pdf

⁸ Styles et al. (2024). <https://www.climatecouncil.ie/media/CBWG%20Report%20GOBLIN%20Model.pdf>

going it alone in Europe, and overlooking the substantial economic benefits that could accrue from development of bio-based industries that store carbon through cascading value chains. Cascading use of wood from commercial forestry, for example, has been shown to deliver strong and sustained climate mitigation over century timescales under multiple decarbonisation pathways in a UK context⁹, similar to Ireland.

Recommendations

Based on the above evidence, we make the following recommendations, which may be within the remit of the Joint Committee on Climate Environment and Energy to consider.

Request the CCAC to revise their carbon budgets proposal to elucidate scenarios that comply with a more robust definition of climate neutrality aligned with the Paris Agreement.

Request the CCAC, or another independent body, to transparently evaluate (implications of) a range of “climate neutrality” definitions that could be used to operationalise the legally binding climate neutrality goal set out in Ireland’s Climate and Low Carbon Development Act 2021. This evaluation could be used to justify any working definition of climate neutrality for national climate policy that deviates from the widely accepted “net-zero” GHG emissions target used by the EU, and many advanced countries. A robust, working definition of climate neutrality is urgently needed to establish appropriate long-term agriculture and land use policy.

Request release of the Land Use Review Phase 2 report, which was submitted to ministers in May 2025 and contains scenarios that illustrate some of key choices and options for Ireland’s agriculture and land sector to achieve climate neutrality by 2050.

⁹ Forster et al. (2021). <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-021-24084-x>